
**AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF PROFITABILITY ANALYSIS IN
PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRIES OF INDIA**

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ABSTRACT

Financial statement analysis is often divided into two sub-parts i.e. "Profitability Analysis" and "Risk Analysis". This is a natural division since much of our thinking about any firm's performance is influenced by our study of the relationship between risk and return in finance. This paper represents an empirical study which examines the profitability from different perspectives of Pharmaceutical industries in India with a data of 10 years from 2002 to 2011 and 07 major pharmaceutical companies have been considered as sample units. For this analytical study, the researcher has used Ratio Techniques for analysis and to test hypothesis Single Factor ANOVA (F-test) has been applied. The study reveals that Glaxosmithkline remained an outperforming player over the last decade in the pharmaceutical industry with leading in the profitability from the different perspectives and Ranbaxy could not match the pace of the profitability with that of the industry average.

Key words: *Pharmaceutical Industries, Profitability Analysis, F-test ANOVA (single factor).*

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INTRODUCTION:

The Indian Pharmaceutical industry is highly fragmented with about 24,000 players (around 330 in the organised sector). The top ten companies make up for more than a third of the market. The Indian pharma industry grew by a robust 18% YoY in 2011 to ` 565 bn (approx. US\$ 12.5 bn). It accounts for about 1.4% of the world's pharma industry in value terms and 10% in volume terms. Besides the domestic market, Indian pharma companies also have a large chunk of their revenues coming from exports.

India is the world's fourth largest producer of pharmaceuticals by volume, accounting for around 8% of global production. In value terms, production accounts for around 1.5% of the world total. The Indian pharmaceutical industry directly employs around 500,000 people and is highly fragmented. While there are around 270 large R&D based pharmaceutical companies in India, including multinationals, government-owned and private companies, there are also around 5,600 smaller licensed generics manufacturers, although in reality only around 3,000 companies are involved in pharmaceutical production. Most small firms do not have their own production facilities, but operate using the spare capacity of other drug manufacturers.

The Indian Pharmaceutical sector is highly fragmented with more than 20,000 registered units. It has expanded drastically in the last two decades. The leading 250 pharmaceutical companies control 70% of the market with market leader holding nearly 7% of the market share. The pharmaceutical industry in India meets around 70% of the country's demand for bulk drugs, drug intermediates, pharmaceutical formulations, chemicals, tablets, capsules, orals and injectibles. There are about 250 large units and about 8000 Small Scale Units, which form the core of the pharmaceutical industry in India (including 5 Central Public Sector Units).

LITERATURE REVIEW:

A study by Amarjit Gill¹, Nahum Biger², Neil Mathur³ (2010), under the title "The Relationship Between Working Capital Management And Profitability: Evidence from the United States", the aim of this paper is to find the relationship between working capital management and profitability. A sample of 88 American firms listed on New York Stock Exchange for a period of 3 years from 2005 to 2007 was selected. We found statistically significant relationship between the cash conversion cycle and profitability, measured through gross operating profit. It follows that managers can create profits for their companies by handling correctly the cash conversion cycle and by keeping accounts receivables at an

optimal level. The study contributes to the literature on the relationship between the working capital management and the firm's profitability.

Mark T. Soliman (February, 2004), under his study titled with "Using Industry-Adjusted DuPont Analysis to Predict Future Profitability" investigated whether using industry-adjusted DuPont analysis is a useful tool in predicting future changes in RNOA. In contrast to prior research that used economy-wide targets and found that these components were not useful in forecasting, and he found that these components were informative when industry-adjusted and that using them would help predict future changes in RNOA in both in-sample and out-of-sample forecasting tests.

Agarwal, V.K (1978), in his study entitled "Size, profitability and growth of some manufacturing Industries", highlighted the relationship between profitability measures as profit/net assets and size expressed total sales for 7 Indian Manufacturing Industries viz. Cotton, Spinning and Weaving, Cement, Cotton ginning, Jute, Textiles, Paper and Pulp, Sugar and Aluminium for the period 1962-1972. The relationship between the size and profitability was observed in cotton spinning and aluminium industry, while in the case of cement and cotton spinning and ginning industry no such relationship was observed.

Kumar.P (1985), in his study on "Corporate growth and profitability in the larger Indian companies", has examined the relationship between profitability and growth in 83 large companies in India's corporate sector during 1969-79. The study reveals a significant inter-study. The very low value of R² in all the cases shows that only a small fraction of the growth of firms in India corporate sector has been explained by profitability.

S. Chandrakumarmangalam and P. Govindasamy (2010), had analyzed under their study - "Leverage" - An Analysis and its Impact on Profitability with Reference to Selected Cement Companies in India, that the leverage and profitability and growth are related and the leverage is having impact on the profitability of the firm.

N. Venkanaramana and K. Ramakrishnaiah (2012), under their study titled with "Profitability and Financial Performance - A Case study on selected Cement companies in India" analyzed that the profitability of the selected companies have a favourable trends towards in terms of Return on Equity Ratio, Return on Capital Employed.

A.Bhunia, S.Mukhuti and Gautam Roy (2011), under their study "Financial Performance Analysis - A Case Study" found that Indian Public Sector Pharmaceutical enterprises' liquidity position was strong. However, financial stability of the selected companies showed a downward trend and consequently the financial stability of the selected companies has been decreasing at an intense rate.

Bhargav H. Pandya (2012), under his study “Financial Analysis of Tata Steel Ltd. – A Case Study revealed that the company performed well in terms of return available to all the investors and also offered a higher return to equity shareholders.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

This study attempts to analyze the profitability of the Selected Pharma companies in terms of Gross profit ratio, Operating margin ratio, Net profit ratio, Return on Capital Employed (ROCE), Return on Net Worth and Earnings per Share (EPS).

Hypothesis of the Study:

1. Gross profit ratio is uniform in the sample units.
2. Operating margin ratio is uniform in the sample units.
3. Net profit ratio is uniform in the sample units.
4. Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) ratio is uniform in the sample units.
5. Return on Net Worth ratio is uniform in the sample units.
6. Earnings per Share (EPS) ratio is uniform in the sample units.

Tools and Techniques:

For the purpose of analysis the researcher has used ‘Ratio Technique’ and to test hypothesis ‘Single Factor ANOVA (F-test) has been applied which is one of the statistical techniques that helps in analyzing the consistency, stability and overall trends in different profitability measurements of the selected companies.

EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS:

1. Gross Profit Ratio

Gross profit ratio is one of the several measures of profitability and it is useful to gauge the efficiency of company and to check how much money is left over to pay for operating expenses. This ratio demonstrates how well the business is efficiently producing the products. It shows how well the products are priced given the direct wages and variable costs it takes to create them. The better the ratio is, the higher the profit potential will be.

$$\text{Ratio} = \frac{\text{Gross Profits}}{\text{Net Sales}} * 100$$

Table 1 represents the gross profit ratios of the selected companies. It can be seen that the industry average on an aggregate basis remained 19.21% as against which Glaxosmith showed the highest average gross profit ratio of 32.57% followed by Dr. Reddy’s (23.17%), Cipla (21.67%), Lupin (16.64%), Sun Pharma (13.87%), Ranbaxy (13.49%) and Cadila (13.06%). The company with higher GP ratio reflects the efficiency in production whereas the company with lower GP ratios compared to industry average will find it difficult to

recover its operating expenses and to build up reserves after paying all fixed interest charges and dividends.

Table 2 shows the calculation of single factor ANOVA wherein, F-calculated (7.55) is greater than F-critical (2.25) leading to the conclusion that the gross profit ratios of the selected companies differ significantly.

Table 1

Gross Profit Ratio (%)									
Year	Sun Pharma	Dr. Reddy's	Cipla	Lupin	Ranbaxy	Glaxosmith	Cadila	Mean	S.D.
2002	29.21	40.11	24.78	14.31	23.09	21.27	16.98	24.25	7.91
2003	33.63	32.05	22.45	12.29	24.14	27.28	17.34	24.17	7.09
2004	0.00	23.48	22.30	19.20	16.90	31.61	19.16	18.95	8.91
2005	0.00	13.63	22.69	10.44	4.90	32.25	19.47	14.77	10.18
2006	27.81	18.65	23.86	17.07	14.39	35.48	20.31	22.51	6.69
2007	26.73	38.66	24.27	16.70	7.51	38.62	20.23	24.67	10.50
2008	6.10	12.58	17.16	18.83	2.07	35.32	11.83	14.84	9.96
2009	0.79	14.11	20.88	17.18	10.52	35.67	9.60	15.54	10.12
2010	9.86	19.70	21.68	20.58	18.31	35.44	1.31	18.13	9.80
2011	4.58	18.72	16.65	19.75	13.10	32.74	(5.67)	14.27	11.27
Mean	13.87	23.17	21.67	16.64	13.49	32.57	13.06	19.21	6.61
S.D.	13.05	9.71	2.64	3.16	7.00	4.77	8.48	4.11	3.63

(Source: Data self compiled and made available from www.moneycontrol.com)

Table 2

ANOVA

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	3058.62635	6	509.77	7.5523	4.01E-06	2.24640798
Within Groups	4252.412	63	67.499			
Total	7311.03835	69				

2. Operating Margin Ratio

Operating margin ratio provides a lot of important information to its business owners regarding cost control. It shows how much case is thrown off after most of the expenses are met. A high operating margin means that a company has good cost control and that sales are increasing faster than costs, which is an optimal situation for the company.

$$\text{Ratio} = \frac{\text{Profits Before Interest and Tax}}{\text{Net Sales}} * 100$$

Calculations of operation margin ratio are presented in the Table 3. It can be realized from the table that against industry average of 19.41%, Glaxosmith reported an aggregate average of 31.46% followed by Dr. Reddy's (23.53%), Cipla (22.53%), Lupin (19.48%), Ranbaxy (15.16%), Cadila (14.08%) and Sun Pharma (9.62%). Operating profit margin illustrates how efficiently the managers of a company using business operations to generate the profits. The reason why Sun Pharma and Cadila stood last can be visible from the table where Sun Pharma incurred operating loss in the year 2007 and did not realize any profit for the year 2004 and 2005. All these caused Sun Pharma on an aggregate basis to earn lower operating margin wherein case of Cadila the operating margin has been continuously declining from the year 2008 till 2010 and in the year 2011 it had become negative showing poor efficiency of the management.

Table 4 indicates the calculations of single factor ANOVA wherein, F-calculated (9.73) is greater than F-critical (2.25) drawing to the conclusion that the operating margin ratio is not uniform during the study period of the selected companies.

Table 3

Operating Margin Ratio (%)									
Year	Sun Pharma	Dr. Reddy's	Cipla	Lupin	Ranbaxy	Glaxosmith	Cadila	Mean	S.D.
2002	29.16	38.32	23.77	21.12	23.54	19.65	16.99	24.65	6.60
2003	33.32	30.03	21.87	18.09	23.93	24.90	18.74	24.41	5.21
2004	0.00	20.87	21.96	23.23	16.58	29.59	16.21	18.35	8.57
2005	0.00	10.53	22.41	11.95	5.01	29.83	17.22	13.85	9.45
2006	1.16	15.82	23.27	18.35	15.17	32.18	18.61	17.79	8.66
2007	(3.28)	35.08	23.07	16.79	9.31	35.72	17.91	19.23	12.82
2008	8.38	17.42	20.27	21.01	5.39	36.29	16.19	17.85	9.29
2009	2.91	18.95	23.78	19.43	13.62	36.54	14.34	18.51	9.55
2010	16.63	24.76	24.63	22.79	22.35	36.27	6.08	21.93	8.46
2011	7.90	23.50	20.27	22.08	16.66	33.61	(1.52)	17.50	10.55
Mean	9.62	23.53	22.53	19.48	15.16	31.46	14.08	19.41	6.70
S.D.	12.10	8.31	1.39	3.22	6.62	5.33	6.26	3.17	3.38

(Source: Data self compiled and made available from www.moneycontrol.com)

Table 4

ANOVA

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	3142.727214	6	523.788	9.72748	1.44E-07	2.246407983
Within Groups	3392.30977	63	53.8462			
Total	6535.036984	69				

3. Net Profit Ratio

Net profit ratio is used to measure the overall profitability and it indicates the firm's capacity to face adverse economic conditions like – increased market competition, economic downturn and a sudden decrease in market demand for the business products. The higher the ratio is, the more effective the company is in converting revenue into actual profits.

$$\text{Ratio} = \frac{\text{Profits After Tax}}{\text{Net Sales}} * 100$$

Table 5

Net Profit Ratio (%)									
Year	Sun Pharma	Dr. Reddy's	Cipla	Lupin	Ranbaxy	Glaxosmith	Cadila	Mean	S.D.
2002	24.39	29.67	17.95	8.05	20.43	11.74	12.28	17.79	7.11
2003	28.98	24.81	16.81	7.08	20.72	15.03	7.91	17.33	7.58
2004	25.29	16.47	15.76	12.34	13.81	23.61	12.30	17.08	4.90
2005	24.78	4.06	18.02	7.19	5.78	32.83	11.49	14.88	10.00
2006	25.85	10.08	20.12	10.98	9.07	33.63	12.43	17.45	8.71
2007	26.69	29.01	18.41	14.89	14.33	32.50	13.42	21.32	7.31
2008	31.01	13.57	16.43	16.30	(22.02)	32.36	13.17	14.40	16.63
2009	31.43	13.20	14.58	14.09	11.72	25.74	13.31	17.72	7.08
2010	33.99	18.48	18.97	17.52	19.74	25.05	20.39	22.02	5.38
2011	42.46	16.84	14.98	18.03	(39.11)	17.11	20.57	12.98	23.00
Mean	29.49	17.62	17.20	12.65	5.45	24.96	13.73	17.30	7.39
S.D.	5.31	7.78	1.70	3.97	18.98	7.66	3.69	2.68	5.50

(Source: Data self compiled and made available from www.moneycontrol.com)

Table 6

ANOVA

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	3822.201	6	637.0335	7.431412	4.87E-06	2.246408
Within Groups	5400.469	63	85.72173			
Total	9222.669	69				

The overall profitability based on sales i.e. Net Profit ratios of the selected companies are visible in Table 5. The industry average on an aggregate basis remained 17.30% which shows sound profitability of the industry as a whole. However, as compared to the previously calculated gross profitability and operating profitability here the results are somewhat different. Sun Pharma which showed lower operating profitability here stood the first with an aggregate average Net Profitability of 29.49% followed by Glaxosmith (24.96%), Dr. Reddy's (17.62%), Cipla (17.20%), Cadila (13.73%), Lupin (12.65%) and Ranbaxy (5.45%). The lowest average Net Profitability in case of Ranbaxy is because of incurring huge losses in the year 2008 (-22.02%) and -39.11% in the year 2011 which indicates that Ranbaxy will find it difficult to survive in tough times since the company does not have much cushioning against adverse conditions.

The calculations of One-way F-test (ANOVA) are shown in the Table 6. Here, the F-calculated (7.43) is greater than F-critical (2.25) indicating that there is a significant difference of Net Profitability in the sample units.

4. Return on Capital Employed (ROCE):

The prime objective of making investments in any business is to obtain satisfactory return on capital employed. ROCE is considered to be the best measure of profitability in order to assess the overall performance of the business. Higher the ratio, the more efficient the firm is in using its funds.

$$\text{Ratio} = \frac{\text{Profits Before Interest and Tax}}{\text{Total Capital Employed}} * 100$$

The ratio of return on capital employed (ROCE) is depicted in Table 7 as under. Generally a higher ratio is considered since it shows greater efficiency of the firm in utilizing its funds. The Glaxosmith with an aggregate average of 45.42% showed the efficient utilization of its funds followed by Cipla (24.32%), Lupin (20.50%), Cadila (19.82%), Sun Pharma (18.91%), Dr. Reddy's (17.16%) and Ranbaxy (14.52%) against an industry average of 22.95%. Due to inconsistency in earning the profits in case of Ranbaxy, the company stood behind. However, Sun Pharma did well despite the zeros in the year 2004, 2005.

Table 8 shows F-test ANOVA calculations wherein F-calculated (16.89) is greater than F-critical (2.25) leading to the conclusion that the ratio of ROCE is not uniform during the study period in the sample units.

Table 7

Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) (%)									
Year	Sun Pharma	Dr. Reddy's	Cipla	Lupin	Ranbaxy	Glaxosmith	Cadila	Mean	S.D.
2002	34.92	33.01	33.40	17.29	27.56	37.82	10.82	27.83	9.32
2003	35.95	24.31	26.33	16.82	36.69	44.23	18.81	29.02	9.42
2004	0.00	15.78	27.57	30.24	21.73	46.37	20.50	23.17	13.14
2005	0.00	5.34	26.93	12.38	3.07	50.26	18.74	16.67	16.25
2006	14.53	8.90	26.67	17.61	10.05	46.67	19.25	20.53	12.03
2007	16.83	30.79	23.40	18.79	4.93	45.60	20.14	22.93	11.72
2008	24.21	10.55	18.17	25.78	2.52	45.06	17.31	20.51	12.44
2009	24.57	13.46	22.39	22.04	8.03	44.09	20.52	22.16	10.45
2010	17.05	15.27	22.16	22.49	12.82	45.35	27.39	23.22	10.13
2011	21.00	14.20	16.22	21.51	17.81	48.75	24.75	23.46	10.83
Mean	18.91	17.16	24.32	20.50	14.52	45.42	19.82	22.95	9.59
S.D.	11.63	8.76	4.71	4.81	10.75	3.13	4.15	3.36	3.43

(Source: Data self compiled and made available from www.moneycontrol.com)

Table 8

ANOVA

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	6435.08428	6	1072.514	16.88703	1.64936E-11	2.246407983
Within Groups	4001.19912	63	63.5111			
Total	10436.2834	69				

5. Return on Net Worth:

This is one of the most important ratios used for measuring the overall profitability of a firm. This ratio reveals that how profitably the proprietors' funds have been utilized by the firm. Since the primary objective of any business is to maximize its earnings, this ratio also indicates the extent to which this primary objective of the business being achieved. Higher the ratio is, better the results are.

$$\text{Ratio} = \frac{\text{Profits After Tax}}{\text{Shareholders' Funds}} * 100$$

Table 9

Return on Net Worth (RON) (%)									
Year	Sun Pharma	Dr. Reddy's	Cipla	Lupin	Ranbaxy	Glaxosmith	Cadila	Mean	S.D.
2002	31.98	31.53	26.73	21.26	33.12	16.93	12.15	24.81	7.60
2003	33.24	21.70	23.38	19.11	34.23	25.80	16.61	24.87	6.24
2004	27.99	13.83	24.46	32.58	21.02	36.04	26.49	26.06	6.80
2005	27.65	3.16	26.54	16.86	8.92	52.93	21.39	22.49	14.93
2006	31.49	9.33	30.78	28.37	16.19	45.66	22.40	26.32	10.90
2007	25.68	26.91	20.70	34.00	24.34	39.51	23.20	27.76	6.15
2008	24.09	9.87	18.72	33.66	(29.50)	37.41	22.41	16.67	20.66
2009	24.56	10.66	17.89	30.31	14.44	29.12	22.11	21.30	6.82
2010	15.71	14.30	18.31	25.64	22.41	29.19	31.05	22.37	6.08
2011	20.71	14.84	14.54	25.69	(158.61)	22.42	29.20	(4.46)	63.13
Mean	26.31	15.61	22.21	26.75	(1.34)	33.50	22.70	20.82	10.35
S.D.	5.14	8.22	4.76	5.82	55.10	10.38	5.27	8.94	17.16

(Source: Data self compiled and made available from www.moneycontrol.com)

Table 10

ANOVA

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	7499.011709	6	1249.835	2.370013	0.03970129	2.246407983
Within Groups	33223.29044	63	527.3538			
Total	40722.30215	69				

Any share holder usually invests in the company to earn the maximum possible returns or continues the investment to maximize the earnings over a period of time. The ratios of Return on Net Worth are shown in Table 9. Glaxosmith with an aggregate average of 33.50% is leading followed by Lupin (26.75%), Sun Pharma (26.31%), Cadila (22.70%), Cipla (22.21%), Dr. Reddy's (15.61%) and Ranbaxy with negative return of 1.34%. since these ratios reveal how well the resources of the firms are being used, generally a higher ratio is preferable. The negative ratio of Ranbaxy indicates that the company is lacking very much in utilizing the funds and the investors will not find it attractive to invest in such a company since the other players provide a better opportunity to earn a fair return. Huge losses during the year 2008 and 2011 have thrown Ranbaxy away from the competition.

The Table 10 indicates the calculations of ANOVA where, F-calculated (2.37) is greater than F-critical (2.25) carrying out the conclusion that the ratio of Return on Net Worth differs significantly.

6. Earnings per Share:

EPS represents the earnings available to equity shareholders per share. EPS remains industry standard in determining the corporate profitability for shareholders. EPS ratio calculated for a no. of years indicates whether or not the earning power of the company has increased or not.

$$\text{Ratio} = \frac{\text{Profits After Tax} - \text{Preference share Dividends}}{\text{Total no. of Equity shares}}$$

Table 11

Earnings per Share (Rs.)									
Year	Sun Pharma	Dr. Reddy's	Cipla	Lupin	Ranbaxy	Glaxosmith	Cadila	Mean	S.D.
2002	36.33	60.07	39.20	17.71	33.62	13.17	11.26	30.19	16.16
2003	24.83	51.24	41.31	18.08	42.84	23.13	12.87	30.61	13.37
2004	25.84	37.01	51.14	36.37	28.38	38.15	22.75	34.23	8.86
2005	16.48	8.55	13.66	21.02	5.69	59.28	20.92	20.80	16.60
2006	24.83	27.53	20.26	45.52	10.21	64.40	26.26	31.29	16.67
2007	32.52	70.09	8.59	37.60	16.56	63.48	16.30	35.02	22.18
2008	48.96	28.26	9.02	54.02	(24.85)	68.07	18.80	28.90	29.17
2009	61.09	33.29	9.99	50.35	13.61	60.48	19.48	35.47	20.32
2010	43.39	50.11	13.47	72.96	27.29	66.55	36.87	44.38	19.44
2011	13.36	52.78	11.96	18.15	(72.32)	50.84	29.81	14.94	38.87
Mean	32.76	41.89	21.86	37.18	8.10	50.76	21.53	30.58	13.34
S.D.	14.16	17.32	15.02	17.82	32.10	18.44	7.40	7.69	7.72

(Source: Data self compiled and made available from www.moneycontrol.com)

Table 12

ANOVA

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	12464.33838	6	2077.39	5.301279	0.000177281	2.246407983
Within Groups	24687.5446	63	391.8658			
Total	37151.88298	69				

If it is about analyzing profitability from different viewpoints, the profitability analysis is said to be incomplete if we do not consider the profitability from the viewpoint of shareholders. Table 11 depicts the earnings per share (EPS) of the selected companies over the last decade. The industry average on an aggregate basis is Rs.30.58 as against which Glaxosmith scored the highest average EPS of Rs.50.76 followed by Dr. Reddy's (Rs.41.89), Lupin (Rs.37.18), Sun Pharma (Rs.32.76), Cadila (Rs.21.53) and Ranbaxy (Rs.8.10). EPS remains the industry standard in determining the corporate profitability. The highest EPS was of Rs.72.96 achieved by Lupin in the year 2010 and the next highest EPS was of Rs.70.09 achieved by

Dr. Reddy's in the year 2007 as against this, the lowest or even negative EPS of Rs.72.32 was registered by Ranbaxy during the year 2011.

Table 12 shows the calculations of ANOVA wherein F-calculated (5.30) is greater than F-critical (2.25) indicating that the EPS of the selected companies is not uniform during the study period.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY:

Glaxosmithkline showed its greatest ability and consistency to control its manufacturing costs and also in managing the margins it makes on the products it purchases or sells.

Operating profitability shows the success rate of the managers. Glaxosmithkline and Dr. Reddy's Laboratories with the highest operating margins showed that their sales were increasing faster than the costs showing a highly liquid position of both the companies.

Sun Pharma showed the highest Net Profitability indicating the efficiency of the company to control its costs and the same can be seen in case of Glaxosmithkline whereas Ranbaxy registered the lowest average Net Profitability indicating its poor efficiency in managing the costs.

The highest average ROCE ratio of Glaxosmithkline shows that the company has gained advantage of financial leverage. Even Cipla and Lupin also performed well.

In case of Return on Shareholders' funds – Glaxosmithkline remained an outperformer. All the players except Ranbaxy registered the profitability and competitive strength over the last decade.

Ceteris paribus i.e. other things being equal, the only way to grow individual shareholders claim to profit and to generate return on investment – is to increase EPS. This can be visible in case of all the selected companies however the two extremes are Glaxosmithkline with the highest average EPS and Ranbaxy with the lowest average EPS.

CONCLUSION:

Ratio Analysis is helpful for any shareholder, investor, creditor, banker or any other party who is concerned with the financial performance of the company. Single factor ANOVA technique helps in analyzing the significance of empirical study by comparing different ratios over a period of time which provides a good sense to the management of the company as well as to the relevant shareholders. The results of this empirical study reveal that Glaxosmithkline remained an outperformer of the Pharmaceutical industries of India whereas Cipla remained consistent and next best after the Glaxosmithkline. Dr. Reddy's Laboratories, Lupin and Sun

pharma did well during the study period. Ranbaxy could not match the pace of Profitability rate with that of the industry average.

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